

Modeling Linear and Nonlinear Inductive Effects in Superconducting Planar Circuits*

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Abstract: Superconducting planar circuits possess properties that can be very different from their normal-metal counterparts, which makes modeling efforts more complicated for superconducting components. In this paper we present closed-form expressions for the resistance and internal inductance per unit length of superconducting planar transmission lines in terms of the relevant material parameters. We also include a simple calculation of the nonlinear response of superconducting devices based on a current-dependent superconducting penetration depth. Taken together, these two descriptions can be used to predict the linear and nonlinear response of superconducting planar devices in a manner that is conducive to use in circuit design. The results of these calculations compare well with 76 K measurements of coplanar waveguide transmission lines and resonators fabricated from thin films of the high T_c superconductor $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7.8}$.

INTRODUCTION

Superconductors are becoming increasingly important for high-performance microwave applications, such as for filters in receiver front ends for wireless base stations [1]. Values of surface resistance for superconducting materials can be more than two orders of magnitude smaller than for copper, and enable highly selective filters that have very low loss [2]. With the high- T_c class of superconductors, such very low surface resistance values can be obtained at temperatures above 60 K, which are easily accessible using current cryocooler technology. It is therefore important to be able to accurately model the electrodynamic response of planar circuits fabricated from these materials. However, the dynamics of the superconducting charge carriers are different from that of normal charge carriers in several significant ways. Due to the Meissner effect, superconductors screen electromagnetic fields differently than normal conductors. One consequence of this is the fact that the relevant skin depth for superconductors is independent of frequency up to very high frequencies. This also leads to an internal inductance that is much larger than that of normal metals, and which can also depend strongly on temperature. For the above reasons, many microwave-frequency circuit-modeling programs have difficulty incorporating superconducting elements. Many such programs describe superconductors simply as lossless conductors, an approach that ignores the contribution of the internal inductance entirely. An accurate calculation of circuit

parameters for superconducting elements must necessarily take into account this internal contribution to the total inductance.

In addition to an enhanced internal inductance, another property of superconductors that must be treated differently from the corresponding property in normal conductors is the nonlinear response. If current densities become sufficiently large, the superconducting charge carriers can depair. This means that the internal inductance of superconducting materials depends on the applied current as well as the temperature. A current-dependent inductance will produce familiar nonlinear effects such as intermodulation distortion and harmonic generation. Such deleterious nonlinear effects can seriously compromise the benefits of superconducting components and must be addressed in many practical circuit applications, preferably beginning at the device design stage.

In order to more effectively exploit the benefits offered by superconducting microwave components, a design tool is needed that can accurately model planar circuits incorporating superconducting elements. Such a design tool would also ideally take into account the potential nonlinear response of the superconducting material. In this paper we describe our efforts to model both the linear and the nonlinear response of superconducting planar circuits. We first describe the development of a quasi-closed-form expression for both the (linear) internal inductance and loss for a number of different superconducting planar geometries, including microstrip, stripline, coplanar waveguide, and coplanar strips. The calculation of the internal inductance is presented here for the first time, and can also be applied to the internal inductance associated with normal-metal conductors. We then proceed to describe how the nonlinear contribution to the superconductor internal inductance can be modeled based on a current-dependent superconducting penetration depth. For both the linear and nonlinear properties, we compare the results of our calculations with measurements of coplanar waveguide transmission lines and resonators fabricated from high-temperature superconductors and measured with a cryogenic microwave probe station. We believe that our models for both the linear and nonlinear response of superconducting planar circuits will prove to be valuable tools for designing and developing high-performance superconducting microwave components.

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CALCULATION OF RESISTANCE AND INTERNAL INDUCTANCE

In previous work [3], the electromagnetic fields in the vicinity of an edge of a conducting strip have been investigated with a matched asymptotic expansion technique. With this asymptotic solution of the fields, the power loss in the region local to the edge was determined accurately. It has been demonstrated that this accurate representation of the power loss near an edge can be used to obtain closed-form expressions for the conductor loss (i.e., the attenuation constant α) for planar structures [3]-[5]. With the expression for the attenuation constant given in [3]-[5], the resistance R per unit length is well approximated by

$$R \approx 2 Z_0 \alpha \approx \frac{\text{Re}[Z_{sm}]}{2} G \quad (1)$$

where G is a geometry factor given by

$$G = \int_{C_{\Delta R}} \left(\frac{J}{I} \right)^2 dl \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), I is the total current, J is the surface current density for the planar circuit with infinitely thin perfect conductors, $C_{\Delta R}$ is the contour of the conducting strip with a small stopping distance Δ_R just before the edge removed, (see [3] for details; see also Fig. 1), and Z_{sm} is the modified Horton surface impedance [6]. This boundary condition takes into account coupling from the top and bottom side of the strip and is given by

$$Z_{sm} = j \sqrt{\frac{\mu_c}{\epsilon_c}} [\cot(k_c t) + \csc(k_c t)], \quad (3)$$

where μ_c and ϵ_c are respectively the permeability and permittivity, k_c is the complex wave-number in the medium, and t is the strip thickness. For a superconductor, k_c is given by

$$k_c = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sqrt{1 + 2j \left(\frac{\lambda}{\delta_{nf}} \right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

where λ is the superconducting penetration depth, and δ_{nf} is the normal-fluid skin depth, related to the normal-fluid conductivity σ_1 by

$$\delta_{nf} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\mu_0 \omega \sigma_1}}. \quad (5)$$

The factor G is a function of the geometry of the planar structure and is given for a microstrip and stripline by

$$G_\mu = G_{SL} = \frac{2}{w \pi^2} \ln \left(\frac{w}{\Delta_R} - 1 \right), \quad (6)$$

where W is the strip width. For coplanar waveguide (CPW) and coplanar-strips (CPS) the corresponding expression is $G_{CPW} = G_{CPS} =$

$$\frac{b^2}{4(b^2 - a^2) K^2(g)} \left\{ \frac{1}{a} \ln \left(\frac{2a}{\Delta_R} \frac{b-a}{b+a} \right) + \frac{1}{b} \ln \left(\frac{2b}{\Delta_R} \frac{b-a}{b+a} \right) \right\}. \quad (7)$$

For the CPW line a is one-half of the center conductor width, b is one-half of the total distance between ground planes, and $g = a/b$. For the CPS line, a is one-half the strip separation, b is the strip width plus one-half the separation, and $g = \sqrt{1 - (a/b)^2}$. In these expressions for G , Δ_R is the stopping distance for calculating the power loss. Values of Δ_R for a wide range of strip thickness versus superconductor penetration depths are given in Fig. 1(a) [7]. The corresponding values for Δ_R for normal conductors can be found in ref. [3].

It can be shown that following a matched asymptotic expansion technique similar to the one given in ref. [3], the stored energy inside the conductor in the region local to the edge can be determined accurately. With this accurate representation of the stored energy near the edge, closed-form expressions for the internal inductance for normal conductors and superconductors can be obtained (details of this calculation will be published separately). From this procedure it can be shown that the internal inductance is given by

$$L_i \approx \frac{\text{Im}[Z_{sm}]}{2 \omega} G. \quad (8)$$

In this expression the geometrical factor G is given above, with the exception that the stopping distance Δ_R in these expressions is replaced with a new stopping distance Δ_X . This new stopping distance Δ_X has been obtained from the calculation of the stored energy in the conductor edge and is given in Fig. 1(b) for a range of superconductor material parameters $t/2\lambda$ and $t/2\delta_{nf}$, for the case of a 90° conductor edge.

To check the validity of this expression, the internal inductance for a CPW line with $a = 60 \mu\text{m}$ and $b = 100 \mu\text{m}$ was calculated and compared to the experimental results in ref. [8]. The comparison is shown in Fig. 2; there is good correlation between the calculation and experimental results. Note that in Fig. 2 it is the kinetic inductance that is determined experimentally. The calculated internal inductance is equal to the kinetic inductance (which arises from kinetic energy in the superconducting condensate) for the superconductor case in the limit of t/δ_{nf} approaching zero. For practical superconductors at temperatures sufficiently below T_c the quantity $t/2\delta_{nf} \ll 1$ and there is essentially no difference between the internal and kinetic inductance.

The ability to use a closed-form expression to calculate the inductance and resistance per unit length for planar geometries is an advantage of the stopping distance formulation. Once Δ_R and Δ_X have been calculated for a given edge profile, there is no need for further numerical calculation to determine R and L for structures having different global conductor geometries. Also, if Δ_R and Δ_X have been calculated for a sufficiently wide material parameter space (values of $t/2\lambda$ and $t/2\delta_{nf}$ in Fig. 1), then the material properties of interest can also change (for example, due to a change in temperature) without the need for

Fig. 1. Stopping distance for loss calculation (a) and internal inductance calculation (b) as a function of $t/2\lambda$. The different curves represent different values for the parameter $t/2\delta_{nr}$. The curves for small values of δ_{nr} fall mostly on top of one another.

further numerical calculations. This makes the expressions given here for the resistance and inductance per unit length valuable for use in circuit design and optimization.

CALCULATION OF THE SUPERCONDUCTOR NONLINEAR RESPONSE

As mentioned previously, another striking difference between superconductors and their normal conducting counterparts is the appearance of nonlinear effects in the superconductor's response at microwave frequencies. The nonlinear response can arise in a superconductor because the internal inductance can depend on the applied current density in some cases. For instance, for sufficiently large current densities the superconducting charge carriers can depair, reducing the

Fig. 2: Comparison of measured kinetic inductance[8] and calculated internal inductance for a series of coplanar waveguide resonators.

superconducting carrier density and increasing the internal inductance. These nonlinear effects can be described by assuming that the superconducting penetration depth depends on current density: $\lambda \equiv \lambda(J)$. A simple form for $\lambda(T, J)$ is given by [9]:

$$\lambda^2(T, J) = \lambda^2(T) \left[1 + \left(\frac{J}{J_0(T)} \right)^2 \right], \quad (9)$$

where J is the current density and J_0 is referred to as the nonlinear scaling current density. This form for $\lambda(T, J)$ is consistent with depairing effects mentioned above, but is also consistent with pair-breaking by other means such as crystalline defects, or with nonlinear response due to the motion of magnetic vortices. We will assume this form for $\lambda(T, J)$ and treat J_0 as a material parameter that must be determined empirically, much like the penetration depth $\lambda(T)$ and the normal fluid conductivity $\sigma_1(T)$. Throughout this analysis, we do not make any specific assumptions for the temperature dependence of the superconductor penetration depth $\lambda(T)$.

In order to model nonlinear effects in superconducting microwave devices, we need to calculate the change in inductance for a given structure associated with the change in superconducting penetration depth with current density. We can write the expression for the inductance per unit length for a planar transmission line as

$$L = \frac{\mu_0 \int (H^2 + \lambda^2 J^2) dS}{(\int J dS)^2}, \quad (10)$$

where the integration is over the cross-sectional area of the particular planar transmission line. We then write the total inductance per unit length as a sum of linear and nonlinear terms:

$$L(I) = L_0 + \Delta L(I) = L_0 + L' I^2, \quad (11)$$

where L_0 includes the external inductance as well as the linear contribution to the internal inductance. We obtain the following expression for L' :

$$L' = \frac{\mu_0 \lambda^2(T)}{J_0^2} \frac{\int J^4 dS}{(\int J dS)^4}, \quad (12)$$

where the integration is over the conductor's cross-section. The expansion of $L(I)$ in Eq. (11) is valid as long as the nonlinear contribution to the total inductance is small, which is true for the superconductor cases considered here. In order to evaluate the above integral, one needs to know the current distribution for the particular geometry under study, which must be re-calculated numerically for each different structure with each different set of material parameters. This is in contrast to the stopping distance formulation discussed above for determining the linear contribution to the internal inductance (which requires no further numerical calculations once the stopping distances have been determined). We calculate the current density distribution for use in Eq. (12) using the $J=0$ limit for $\lambda(T, J)$, which is also appropriate for weakly nonlinear systems. Once the nonlinear contribution to the inductance has been calculated for the transmission-line geometry of interest, it is straightforward to calculate standard nonlinear effects such as harmonic generation and intermodulation distortion, as will be shown below.

COMPARISONS TO MEASUREMENTS: $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7.5}$ DEVICES AT 76 K

In order to verify our calculations, we wish to compare our calculated results with measured data on superconducting devices measured at cryogenic temperatures. For this purpose we fabricate CPW transmission lines and resonators from thin films of the high- T_c superconductor $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7.5}$ (YBCO). We characterize the linear response of these devices by measuring the quality factor of a CPW resonator at 76 K, and we characterize the nonlinear response by measuring third harmonic generation of CPW transmission lines also at 76 K. Comparing our calculated results with these measurements demonstrates the validity and applicability of our calculations to superconducting systems of technological interest.

We fabricated superconducting thin film samples of YBCO on 0.5 mm thick LaAlO_3 substrates using pulsed laser deposition. The c-axis oriented YBCO films reported here were 400 nm and 50 nm in thickness, 16 mm by 16 mm in area, and were grown from the same target under nominally identical deposition conditions. The films have a superconducting transition temperature T_c greater than 90 K. In order to calculate the linear and nonlinear response of devices fabricated from these films, we need to accurately know several key material parameters: the normal fluid penetration depth $\delta_{nf}(T)$, the penetration depth $\lambda(T, J=0)$, and the current-dependent term in the penetration depth (quantified by the

current density scale $J_0(T)$), all at the temperature of interest. We obtained these parameters by a series of measurements performed on the thin-film material before it was patterned into a device geometry. We obtained information on the penetration depth by mutual-inductance techniques performed at 10 kHz, which gave the value of the penetration depth $\lambda(T, J=0)$ and also the nonlinear current-density scale $J_0(T)$ [10], both at 76 K. We then obtained the normal fluid skin depth $\delta_{nf}(T)$ from sapphire-loaded dielectric resonator measurements of the unpatterned thin films [11]. In this way we were able to obtain independent measures of the relevant material parameters of our superconducting thin films at 76 K: $\lambda(T, J=0)$, $\delta_{nf}(T)$, and $J_0(T)$. Values obtained for these material parameters at 76 K for the two films reported on here are summarized in Table I.

Once our superconducting thin films had been characterized, they were patterned with multiple different CPW devices using Ar ion milling. Gold contact pads were deposited with a Ti adhesion layer by electron beam evaporation and a lift-off technique. For the measurements described here, the CPW structures had a center-conductor width of 21 μm and a gap spacing (distance between center conductor and ground planes on either side) of 40 μm . Our CPW resonator was 11.53 mm in length, and the transmission lines ranged in length from 1.68 mm to 10.5 mm.

Our patterned devices were measured at 76 K using a cryogenic microwave probe station [12]. This probe station was specially adapted so that the thin-film devices under test are cooled under vacuum along with movable coplanar microwave probes, so that multiple devices can be measured at a given cryogenic temperature during a single experiment. Upon cooling our YBCO samples to 76 K, we measured the unloaded quality factor Q_u vs. frequency for the patterned CPW resonator in order to compare with the results of our calculations. From our unpatterned measurements of these two films, we obtained the parameters listed in table I. We used these values for the penetration depth $\lambda(T, J=0)$ and normal fluid conductivity $\sigma_1(T)$ ($\sigma_1(T)$ is related to the normal fluid skin depth $\delta_{nf}(T)$ by $\delta_{nf}(T) = (2/\mu_0\omega\sigma_1(T))^{1/2}$) in order to

Table 1. Material parameters for the superconducting films used for devices.

	Film A	Film B	Technique
material	YBCO	YBCO	
thickness (nm)	400	50	
λ (J=0) @ 76 K (nm)	274	285	Mutual inductance
σ_1 @ 76 K ($10^9/\Omega\text{m}$)	2.71	1.97	Dielectric resonator
J_0 @ 76 K (MA/cm ²)	40 ^a	40	Mutual inductance

^aThe value for J_0 was measured only for the 50 nm film.

calculate the attenuation and phase constant per unit length (α and β respectively) for our YBCO resonator. We then obtained the calculated (unloaded) quality Q_u factor as a function of frequency from the following relation:

$$Q_u = \frac{\beta(\omega)}{2\alpha(\omega)}. \quad (13)$$

The results are plotted in Fig. 3 for the CPW resonators fabricated from two films of different thickness (400 nm and 50 nm). The agreement is excellent using independently determined parameters for $\lambda(T, J=0)$ and $\delta_{in}(T)$ at 76 K. It should be noted that the effect of ignoring the internal inductance in this calculation is to underestimate the value of the unloaded quality factor by approximately 4% for the devices fabricated from the 400 nm film. While the contribution of the internal-inductance term to the total inductance is not large, the internal inductance accounts for all of the temperature-dependent effects in these devices, and is therefore important to include in any device model.

In order to characterize our patterned CPW transmission lines for their nonlinear response we measured the third-harmonic generation as a function of incident microwave power. Previously we calculated the nonlinear contribution to the inductance due to a current-dependent penetration depth. Assuming a quadratic form for the current-dependent inductance per unit length $L(I) = L_0 + L'I^2$, we can simply calculate the third harmonic generated by such a nonlinear inductor, for a single-tone input. We obtain for the power in the third harmonic

Fig. 3. Measured quality factor of a CPW resonator as a function of frequency for two different thickness YBCO films at 76 K. The solid lines are the result of our calculation, using parameters determined from prior measurements of the unpatterned thin film. The resonator had a center conductor linewidth of 21 μm , gap spacing of 40 μm and length 11.5 mm.

$$P_3 = \left[\frac{\omega L' \ell}{2Z_0^2} \right]^2 P_1^3, \quad (14)$$

where ℓ is the transmission line length, Z_0 is the characteristic impedance, and P_1 is the power transmitted in the fundamental mode. If we plot the power in the third harmonic P_3 as a function of the power in the fundamental tone P_1 on a log-log plot we will obtain a line of slope 3 with an intercept determined by the nonlinear inductance term L' . The experimentally relevant term to calculate is the third-order intercept IP_3 , which is given by

$$\log IP_3 = \log \frac{2Z_0^2}{\omega L' \ell}. \quad (15)$$

We show in Fig. 4 an example of the third-harmonic signal generated by one of our CPW transmission lines at 76 K and 3 GHz. As predicted by Eq. 13, the third harmonic increases with incident power with slope 3 on the log-log plot. It follows that we can then specify the third-harmonic response at any power by specifying the third-order intercept point IP_3 . Since IP_3 is related to the nonlinear inductance L' above, we can calculate the magnitude of the third-harmonic signal at any incident power provided the nonlinear scaling current density J_0 , along with the current distribution, are known. Figure 5 shows the calculated values for the third-order intercepts of various lengths for CPW transmission lines fabricated from our two different YBCO films. Also shown are the third-order intercepts calculated assuming a current-dependent penetration depth with the parameter J_0 determined from mutual-inductance measurements of the 50 nm sample only ($J_0 = 40 \text{ MA/cm}^2$).

Fig. 4. Measured power in the third harmonic vs. incident power for a 10.5 mm long transmission line fabricated from the 50 nm YBCO film at 76 K and a fundamental frequency of 3 GHz. The solid line is a fit to slope 3, illustrating extraction of third-order intercept IP_3 .

Fig. 5. Measured and calculated third-order intercepts IP_3 vs. line length for 400 nm and 50 nm YBCO samples at 76 K, 3 GHz fundamental.

We use this J_0 value to calculate the nonlinear response of the 400 nm film as well, since based on previous results [13] we do not expect the value of J_0 for films deposited under similar growth conditions to change significantly with film thickness. The agreement between the measured third-order intercepts and the calculated values is very good for this nonlinear case also.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we have demonstrated how both linear and nonlinear inductive effects can be successfully modeled in order to predict the response of planar circuits fabricated from superconducting components, based on a few material parameters. In addition to providing a valuable tool for simulating actual superconducting circuits, these results also demonstrate how nonlinear effects can be modeled based on a simple *inductive* nonlinearity.

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